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7. ZNANSTVENA KONFERENCA Z MEDNARODNO UDELEŽBO ZA ČLOVEKA GRE: PRIHODNOST ZDAJ!

7th SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE WITH INTERNATIONAL PARTICIPATION
ALL ABOUT PEOPLE: FUTURE FIT!

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**7th SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE WITH INTERNATIONAL PARTICIPATION
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Marija Jevtić, Catherine Bouland

ENVIRONMENTAL CHALLENGES AND THEIR IMPORTANCE FOR MENTAL HEALTH (ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECTS OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT)

The general understanding of mental health and its connection with the environment is defined as a research problem. The WHO underscores the estimate that in 2012 12.6 million people died as a result of living/working in an unhealthy environment. Environmental risk factors such as air, water, soil and noise pollution, chemical exposures, climate change and others contribute to more than 100 different diseases.

The link between mental health and environment has been analysed using a descriptive method. Mental health is considered as disease; not enough attention is paid to the health aspect. It is important to underline that mental, behavioral and neurological disorders accounted for 10% of the global disease burden in 2015 and will increase to 15% by 2020. Depression, drug and alcohol dependence, post-traumatic stress, anxiety, insomnia, autism and attention deficit are threats for the population, healthcare systems, communities, institutions and families.

It is not possible to strictly separate environmental and social factors when acting within the urban environment. Natural and built environment and social factors are intertwined. In the era of urbanisation, their synergies impact the mental health of individuals and the population as a whole. Strengthening positive factors of the environment at local, national and global levels is an imperative. All efforts to increase green areas, improve urban planning and public transportation, decrease noise and support physical activity are important to sustain the mental health capacity of the population.

Key findings and recommendations: Mental health is very poorly resourced at present. Through the SDGs and different national and local development plans, citizens are empowered to improve their mental health through a better environment. It is necessary to focus on all strategies and activities to enhance the mental health capacity of the whole population.

Key words: environment, mental health, sustainable development goals, urbanization, population

